

THE ROLE OF POLITICAL PARTIES IN SOCIETY AND THEIR DUTIES

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Abstract

Since the emergence of political parties, their role in society has been strengthened, and they have been performing certain tasks to ensure the well-being of human life. The contribution of political parties to development can be measured by the level of political consciousness of an individual living in modern society. One of the main tasks of political parties is to increase a person's political consciousness, activity and knowledge. The article focuses on the role of political parties in society and the tasks they should perform in its development.

Key words: political party, society, state, political consciousness, political power, party system, democracy, elections.

Introduction. Let's look at the history of political parties. We can see that they appeared primarily due to the need to create a favourable social-political, legal, economic, and cultural environment for them to live and work in while protecting the interests of people in society.

Political parties, as a complex socio-political phenomenon, are being studied as an object of research in political science from different perspectives. In world science, there are still many debates and disputes about the definition of political parties, their emergence, characteristics and tasks.

Political parties are primarily considered an important political institution that leads society towards development. They try to develop the political consciousness of the population, the electorate, to ensure political activity and thus to ensure the direct or indirect participation of citizens in governance. The fact that the concept of representative democracy has been widely used in political science in recent years means that this process is carried out directly through political parties and that these concepts are interrelated and complement each other.

The ability of political parties to fulfil their tasks at a high level will raise the development of society to a new level and will further strengthen its position and lead to an increase in public confidence in it.

The main part. We can see that the scope of action of political parties while organizing society is related to the main purpose of its activity to ensure

its development. True, not all political parties may serve the development of society, but all of them have the goal of realizing the wishes and desires of certain narrow or wide groups. As the political party as a very complex socio-political phenomenon is deeply researched, we can observe that its new features are revealed and new tasks are created in line with the times. We can divide scholars who study political parties into three groups. Western scientists who studied the activities of the first group of political parties include M. Duverge, M. Weber, J. Sartori, G. Hegel, R. Michels, T. Hobbs, J. Locke, and J.-J. Rousseau. J. Mill, T. Parsons, Z. Neyman, K. Zanda, Russian scientists M. Ostrogorsky, B. Isaev, V. Pugachev, A. Salovev, V. K. Baturin, A. Akmalov, Uzbek scientists M. Kyrgyzboyev, Q. Nazarov, S. Berdikulov, R. Hasanov, Q. Jurayev, H. Odilkoriyev, D. Razzokov, V. Kochkarov, B. Yakubov and others studied.

According to Q. Jurayev, "Political party is the most active part of citizens, connected based on a common ideology, striving to gain, preserve and implement state power, a voluntary union" [1, -P. 199]. Thus, one of the common features of political parties is that their main goal is to gain and maintain power. Almost all political scientists cite the desire for power as the main characteristic of political parties.

According to M. Weber, for political parties to be formed as an institutional political structure, the following should be present in it:

- party leaders and party apparatus;
- party discipline;
- financial resources of the party;
- party press; - party propaganda (advertising) [2, -P. 93].

We believe that it is necessary to pay special attention to these elements when studying the political party from an institutional point of view. Also, we should not forget that the work of the party in the ideological sphere is directly affected by the efficiency of its activity as a structure. Political scientists who have studied political parties based on different approaches have also revealed conclusions about the characteristics of parties in different ways. Indeed, the division of political parties into types is also important. It should not be overlooked that the characteristics of different types of political parties are also different. For example, according to M. Duverje, "Political parties are divided into personnel, mass and ultra-centralized types" [3].

American political scientist J. LaPalombara focuses on three main characteristics of a political party:

1. The existence of a certain political ideology, based on which the program and activities of the political party are built.

2. A high level of institutionalization is expressed in the presence of an organizational structure that permeates all levels of politics.

3. The desire to cover as many people as possible with their influence, both by attracting voters to their side and by expanding the number of party members [4, -P. 286].

In ensuring the development of society, political parties as important political institutions, form public opinion depending on their position concerning power and management. That is, if the party is sympathetic to the existing governing institutions, it can act as an assistant to them, supporting their policies.

According to D. Razzokov and H. Odilkoriev, political parties have the following tasks:

- the development of a specific goal, the party creates its ideology and program and tries to form a public opinion that approves it;

- participation in political activities. In this, certain interests are protected;

- support and encourage the political activity of citizens. In this, the citizen's spirit directs the implementation of the party's goals, and the mass media is used to shape public opinion;

- forming the ruling elite of the party, ensuring communication between the representative bodies of the authorities and the society, forming the mechanism of state and social management together with other political institutions, ensuring the stability of the structures and mechanisms of the authorities;

- improvement of political culture;

- influencing the activities of the parliament and the government;

- educating political leaders;

- active participation in the formation and implementation of the goals facing the state[5, -P. 155].

We should also emphasize that one of the main tasks of a political party is to develop its program goals and development strategy. In the modern world, there are also important questions about what the programs of political parties should be, their positions, and to what extent the impact of globalization on their characteristics.

The world's climate is undergoing drastic changes, problems related to the lack of fresh water, the spread of various epidemiological diseases, the rapid

growth of the population, the increase in the need to ensure food security, and the increase in the need for various other important resources lead to political, economic, military disputes and conflicts between countries. leads to an increase. In such a rapidly changing world, political parties need to update their tasks and enrich their programs with measures and activities aimed at solving these problems.

Judging from the above, today, in addition to the expansion of globalization, the development of modern ICTs also leads to the emergence and development of new forms of political parties. As a clear example of this, we can cite the emerging concepts of "online party" and "virtual party". We believe that these processes, which are characteristic of changes, will lead to the renewal of the tasks of political parties.

In conclusion, we should emphasize that political parties are institutions whose politicized goal is power, which plays an important role in the development of society. They strive for power, which is their highest goal, and try to maintain it, satisfying the needs of their electorate while fulfilling their assigned tasks in society. Also, political parties are carriers of ideology, organizations that increase the political activity of the society and conduct regular research to increase the political consciousness and culture of the electorate.

Based on the above, we offer the following:

- Increasing the amount of research aimed at studying the role of political parties in society and its characteristics;
- Strengthening the continuation of research based on new methods of the factors affecting the renewal and expansion of the tasks of political parties.

References:

1. Jalilov A., Juraev Q. Foundations of civil society. Study guide. State Administration Academy in the presence of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. -T. 2015. p. 264.
2. Weber M. Political work (1895-1919). - M.: Praxis. 2003. 148 p.
3. Achkasova V.A., Gutarova V.A. Political science. - M.: Yurayt. 2005. 308 p.
4. Lantsov S.A. Political science: Uchebnoe posobie. — SPb.: Peter. 2011. — 544 p.
5. Odilkoriev Kh.T., Razzokov D.Kh. Political science. Textbook. "Teacher" NMIU, 2008. p. 344.

